

TRANSPOSITION OF ADVERBS IN ENGLISH SENTENCES

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***Abstract.** The article analyzes the functional transposition of adverbs in English sentences. The research is conducted in a comparative aspect. Examples in English from fiction and their equivalents in Uzbek are given.*

***Keywords:** text, grammar, adverb, English, transposition, sentence.*

One of the important factors in learning English is its morphological and syntactic aspects. In this regard, the study of morphology and syntax, which occupy a special place in linguistics, is relevant today.

It is well known that text performs a communicative function between people. When constructing a text, all units of the level are purposefully hierarchically connected to each other, creating conditions for the formation of the text. It is from this point of view that the study of the information structure of the text and the analysis of the morphological and syntactic means that form its basis are among the important issues. One of the leading fields of modern linguistics is the linguistics of text.

From this point of view, it is important to study the functions, structure and morphological division of an adverb in a sentence.

Let's look at the cases of transposition of adverbs inside the text from the point of view of functionality in a sentence:

1. Cases of verbalization and substantiation of adverbs.

It is known that the main function of adverbs is the modification of verbs. Semantically widespread adverbs focus on the characteristic and imperative feature of the verb. This can be seen from the example below:

1) "Agatha patted her thighs. "Here, here, doggie. Why doesn't he like me?" [2, p.126] – Agata uning sonlarini siladi. "Bu yerga qarang, itga qarang. Nega u meni sevmaydi?"

2) "You two. Out!" [3, p.280] – "Ikkalangiz. Yo'qol."

According to the research of D.S. Kharieva, which deals with the issue of imperative based on the materials of the Russian language, adverbs with a wide range of meanings actualize the concept of intentionality in a given situation, such that

adverbs most directly express the concept of imperative in speech structures (dialogic).

Let us consider another example. In this case, with justification, the adverb retains its ability to convey the idea of location.

“Before him were ranged a square ink-pots, a plastic ash-tray, a telephone.” [3, p.174] – “Uning oldida faqat kvadrat siyoh idishlari, plastik kuldon va telefon bor edi.”

2. Adjectivation. In modern English, the distinction between many homonymous adverbs and adjectives is made on a syntactic basis:

“In one of the upstairs windows a light went on, and a fattish girl in a nightgown came over to draw the curtains.” [3, p.485] – “Yuqori qavatdagi derazalardan birida yorug‘lik yonib, pardani chizish uchun tungi ko‘ylakdagi semiz qiz keldi.”

In this sentence, the adverb upstairs is used as the definition of the noun window. It is the consideration of distributive and positional parameters that can determine and explain the transposition of adverbs.

The productivity of most adverbs in English distinguishes these units from other word classes (noun, adjective). It is necessary to distinguish not only simple combinations involving adverbs, but also complex combinations. Let us look at the derivatives used with affixes.

For example: “It is an honor for an Azteca to die thusly.” [3, p.296] – “Atsteklar uchun shunday o‘lish sharafdir.”

“His daughter Virginia Hicks is here in the hospital, Ruth said. - No! Yes indeed! Husband Lewis brought her in.” [3, p.362] – “Uning qizi Virjiniya Hicks kasalxonasida”, dedi Rut. - Yo‘q! Ha, albatta! Eri Lyuis uni olib keldi.”

When combining the affixes /ly/ and /y/ in adverbs, morpheme patterns are violated, it is known that usually /ly/ is added to adjectives (to form an adverb) or to nouns (to form an adjective), the inflection /y/ is a suffix of adjectives or diminutive forms formed from nouns.

3. Modulation. Modal words should be distinguished from adverbs, which express the speaker's subjective attitude to the expression and belong to the whole sentence (they are not members of the sentence). There are a number of words that, in their modal-evaluative semantics, resemble modal words, but can also act as part of a sentence as adverbs of any other word in the sentence. They can act as transpositional modal words. These are adverbs - apparently, evidently, really, unfortunately.

“Brendel is certainly a fine musician. Indeed, I regard him as one of the greatest pianists of our time. It is indeed a great tragedy that he died so young.” [1, p.728] –

“Brendel, albatta, ajoyib musiqachi. Darhaqiqat, men uni zamonamizning eng buyuk pianinohilaridan biri deb bilaman. Darhaqiqat, uning yosh vafot etgani katta fojiaidir”.

An adverb differs from parts of speech by its free use, does not create a connection with a dependent member, and has no lexical connection with a verb. However, sometimes an adverb can take over the function of attaching to a dependent member. Such cases are corrected in academic grammar and treated as intermediate cases of combining several functions with an adverb:

“She opened wide the window nearest where they sat.” [1, p.560] – “Ular o'tirgan joyga eng yaqin derazani keng ochdi.”

“The bus stop is nearer my house than the underground station.” [1, p.560] – “Avtobus bekati mening uyimga metrodan ko'ra yaqinroq”.

It is difficult to single out such cases, since the smallest semantic changes are taken into account. In the first case with the modal word /indeed/, it is really obvious that all the facts show that this is the case.

In the second case, /indeed/ is present as an adverb that conveys the meaning of “actually”. The adverb /frankly/ expresses the sincerity of the speaker, but it can also play another role. Thus, considering the adverbs in the information structure of the text, we can conclude that each of the adverbs changes the meaning of the verb to which it refers. Each adverb has its own meaning in the sentence and there are cases of their transposition.

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